

**THE CONCEPT OF PRE-CONTRACTUAL LIABILITY IN THE CIVIL
LAW OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract

This article explores the concept pre-contractual liability and origins of the doctrine of culpa in contrahendo, analyzes existing scholarly approaches to its definition and examines expert opinions in the field. It also investigates the institution of pre-contractual liability (culpa in contrahendo) within the civil law of Uzbekistan. The author identifies and analyzes the fragmented legal provisions that partially regulate relations at the negotiation stage. Special attention is given to the principle of good faith as a fundamental tenet of civil law and a key criterion for party behavior during pre-contractual negotiations. Based on an analysis of the norms of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan, the article substantiates the possibility of applying the doctrine of culpa in contrahendo. From a comparative perspective, the author examines the legislation of Germany, Italy, and Russia, where the institution of pre-contractual liability has received formal legal recognition and practical development. The author concludes that the incorporation of similar provisions into the Civil Code of Uzbekistan is necessary to strengthen the principles of good faith, trust, and equality of participants in civil turnover, especially in negotiations, as well as to harmonize national law with modern European legal trends.

Keywords: pre-contractual liability, culpa in contrahendo, good faith, confidentiality, negotiations, promissory estoppel, preliminary contract, freedom of contract, damages, civil liability.

Introduction

In the context of a developing market economy, there is growing activity among participants in civil transactions. The main legal instrument for engaging in civil relations is the contract, which expresses the parties' intention to acquire goods, perform work, provide services, etc. It is reasonable to consider the contract as the final result of the parties' joint efforts. However, civil law allows us to distinguish a separate category of legal relationships that arise during the preparatory stage preceding the conclusion of a contract. These relations are called negotiations and transitional in nature. Their primary purpose is to create the necessary preconditions for the future emergence of a civil law contract. Civil law theory does not exclude the possibility of liability arising during the negotiation process for the conclusion of a contract, which is also known as pre-contractual liability.

Pre-contractual liability is a legal institution that governs compensation for damages caused during negotiations prior to the conclusion of the main contract. In Uzbekistan, there are no direct legal norms regulating this area, which leads to legal gaps in the protection of parties' interests at the negotiation stage. With the ongoing digital transformation and the growth of electronic interactions, the need for clear regulatory provisions governing this institution is increasing. The purpose of this article is to define the concept, features, and content of pre-contractual liability, as well as to determine its place within the civil law of Uzbekistan.

Research Methods

In the course of writing this academic article, a range of scientific methods were employed, including synthesis, analysis, induction, deduction, and the method of comparative analysis.

Results

Various legal facts can serve as grounds for the emergence of pre-contractual legal

relations. However, not all activities of the parties at the preparatory stage can be considered as a legal fact giving rise to civil rights and obligations. The moment of the emergence of pre-contractual legal relations should be considered a situation when the behavior of the parties (or one of them) clearly indicates the intention to conclude a contract or enter into negotiations on its conclusion. Such actions include sending a proposal to conclude an agreement (offer), signing various interim documents — protocols, agreements, memoranda of intent, carrying out agreed expenses related to the preparation of the transaction, initialing the text of the future agreement and other similar actions.

Regardless of the form and procedure chosen by the parties for their negotiations, regulatory oversight of the process generally includes the following key principles:

- Freedom of contract negotiations;
- Good faith conduct by the parties during and after the negotiations;
- The duty to provide accurate and complete information to the counterparty;
- Establishing and maintaining confidentiality of exchanged information, including determination of consequences for its breach;
- Allocation of negotiation-related expenses;
- Liability for violations of the negotiation process.

The content of pre-contractual legal relations is defined either by a general duty of proper conduct during contract formation, primarily, the duty of good faith negotiations or by a duty to conclude a contract in cases provided by law.

The obligation to conduct negotiations in good faith represents a set of norms of proper behavior, the content of which may vary depending on the nature of the future contract, its subject matter, and the specific circumstances of the negotiations.

First and foremost, the duty of good faith in negotiations is based on a fundamental principle of civil law—the principle of good faith. The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (hereinafter — the Civil Code) enshrines a presumption of good faith on the

part of legal participants. In particular, Article 9 of the Civil Code states that good faith, reasonableness, and fairness of participants in civil legal relations are presumed [1].

The core issue lies in determining what constitutes good faith behavior at the negotiation stage, which remains one of the most debated topics in civil law. Legal scholarship has developed specific behavioral criteria that may be considered as meeting the principle of good faith in negotiations.

These include, first, consistency of actions, which implies a need to clearly communicate the reasons for terminating negotiations and to indicate any circumstances or actions of the other party that may affect their continuation. Secondly, informational openness is deemed crucial, which implies a duty to disclose information that is significant to the counterparty, particularly when it would be difficult or impossible for them to obtain it independently, given the nature of the anticipated contract and the relative positions of the parties.

In this context, good faith behavior means proper fulfillment of duties established by law and agreement during the negotiation phase. Such duties include: providing complete and accurate information to the other party; maintaining confidentiality of negotiations and refraining from using disclosed information for personal gain; bearing negotiation-related costs; disclosing relevant facts about participants or circumstances that, due to the nature of the future contract, must be communicated to the counterparty; and participating in the preparation of final or other related documents.

Unfortunately, not all negotiation participants follow these rules, which may give rise to pre-contractual liability, often referred to as *culpa in contrahendo*.

Pre-contractual liability is a specific institution of civil law, expressed in a party's obligation to compensate the counterparty for losses incurred during the negotiation and contract conclusion stages as a result of a breach of pre-contractual obligations established by law or agreement. The scope of this liability includes cases of bad faith during negotiations, provision of false information, withholding material facts, or lack of genuine

intent to conclude a contract.

In Uzbek legislation, the issue of pre-contractual liability remains insufficiently regulated. However, certain norms partially address this area. For example, Article 439 of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan establishes liability for bad faith conduct in the form of evading resolution of disagreements that arise when concluding a supply contract. During such contract negotiations, parties must be guided by the principle of good faith since the norm explicitly imposes an obligation to compensate for losses resulting from inaction in agreeing to contract terms. Therefore, if one party receives a proposal to settle disputed terms but takes no action to reach agreement and fails to inform the counterparty of its refusal to conclude the contract, it may be held liable.

In addition, Article 377 of the Civil Code provides for liability for unjustified evasion from concluding a contract that is binding on the party. In particular, in accordance with this article, a party who does not have sufficient grounds for refusal, but avoids concluding a binding contract, is obliged to compensate the other party for the losses caused. An example is the unlawful refusal of a commercial organization to conclude a public contract (Article 358 of the Civil Code).

Violations of good faith at the pre-contractual stage, including failure to disclose necessary information (*duty of disclosure*), deceit, or coercion may also serve as grounds for claiming actual damages if the contract is subsequently invalidated under Articles 122 and 123 of the Civil Code.

Bad faith actions giving rise to pre-contractual liability may also include unjustified refusal to notarize or register a transaction, as stipulated in Article 112 of the Civil Code.

In addition, Article 380 of the Civil Code provides for the possibility of collecting damages in the event of a participant's evasion from concluding a contract based on the results of the auction or from signing a protocol on the results of the auction.

Other provisions related to pre-contractual liability include Article 427, which imposes liability for unjustified refusal by a seller to conclude a retail sales contract,

particularly if the refusal involves failure to provide the buyer with essential product information.

Despite the presence of these scattered provisions, Uzbek civil legislation still lacks a unified regulatory framework governing the conduct of negotiations and establishing liability measures for violations during that process. This legislative gap reinforces the need for formal implementation of the doctrine of *culpa in contrahendo* by introducing a dedicated article into the Civil Code of Uzbekistan.

Discussion

The historical roots of the doctrine of *culpa in contrahendo* trace back to the work of Rudolf von Jhering, who, in his 1861 study “*Culpa in contrahendo*”, was the first to substantiate the need to impose liability for harm caused during the process of contract formation, even in the absence of a valid agreement [2]. Jhering argued that the party acting in good faith, having suffered damages due to reliance on the appearance of a valid contract, should be entitled to compensation for what he called “negative interest”—i.e., actual losses incurred due to reliance on the negotiation, but without the right to claim lost profits. He asserted that from the moment negotiations begin, a special (quasi-contractual) relationship arises between the parties, generating mutual rights and obligations, the violation of which gives rise to liability for damages [3].

According to G. Faggella, the mere act of entering negotiations constitutes a legally significant fact, and their termination should only be justified by economic reasons. In all other cases, while terminating negotiations is theoretically allowed under the principle of freedom of contract, it should give rise to liability for bad faith conduct at the pre-contractual stage [4].

The doctrine of *culpa in contrahendo* developed gradually in German law. Jhering initially applied it only to violations occurring during contract conclusion, including cases where the deal was found invalid or not concluded. Faggella later expanded the doctrine’s scope to include situations where negotiations were terminated for non-economic reasons.

F. Leonhard went even further, arguing that a party could be held liable for *culpa in contrahendo* even when a valid contract had already been concluded [5].

German tort law did not impose liability for purely economic losses incurred in the preparation for a contract that was ultimately not concluded. Furthermore, the absence of a general tort clause prevented Jhering from classifying such liability under tort law.

Consequently, Jhering concluded that the claim based on *culpa in contrahendo* was of a contractual nature. In his view, when parties begin negotiations, they take on not only an obligation to perform if a contract is concluded but also a duty to show readiness and take reasonable steps toward reaching the agreement. If a defect arises that hinders fulfillment of this secondary duty, it is the contractual obligation that is breached. Therefore, claims for damages in such cases should be considered contractual rather than tortious.

Supporting this view are the provisions of §823 of the German Civil Code, which limit the scope of tort liability by protecting only certain interests and excluding cases where the damage is purely economic [6].

In contrast, Uzbek law approaches this issue differently. According to Article 986 of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan, damage caused by unlawful actions (or inactions) to a person or the property of a citizen, as well as damage to a legal entity, must be compensated in full by the person who caused the harm—including lost profits [7]. Thus, tort liability in Uzbekistan arises not only from harm to a person but also to property, marking a key difference from German law.

Another argument against the contractual classification of this liability under Uzbek law is the absence of a contract between the parties — an essential prerequisite for contractual liability. Therefore, one should refrain from prematurely classifying *culpa in contrahendo* as contractual liability.

This cautious approach is echoed in French civil law, which adopts a different legal framework. Unlike in Germany, where the doctrine of pre-contractual liability had to be

developed to address legal gaps, French law did not face such deficiencies from the outset. This is because tort liability in France has traditionally had a broader scope, allowing for the protection of parties' interests already at the negotiation stage.

According to Articles 1382–1383 of the French Civil Code, any act that causes harm to another creates an obligation to compensate for the damage. This liability covers not only intentional acts but also harm caused by negligence or imprudence [8]. Therefore, a party who suffers losses due to bad faith behavior during negotiations is protected through tort law mechanisms.

Although the idea of *culpa in contrahendo* has long existed in French legal thought, it lacked direct legal codification until the major reform of contract law from 2005–2016, which introduced provisions that explicitly regulate liability for bad faith negotiation [9]. This reform also strengthened the principle of good faith, making it one of the cornerstones of modern French contract law.

A third approach is found in common law jurisdictions. Here, the doctrine of *culpa in contrahendo* has not developed, and the issue of whether liability is tortious or contractual is generally not raised. This is due to the aleatory (risk-based) nature of negotiation in common law, i.e. each party is expected to act in its own economic interest and bear the risk of entering into negotiations with an unreliable partner.

English courts, for instance, generally hold that parties in negotiations are free to pursue their interests by any lawful means, as long as their actions do not involve active misrepresentation. A party may even terminate negotiations strategically, anticipating that the counterparty may resume talks and accept less favorable terms. Thus, the duty of good faith in negotiations is often viewed as inapplicable in practice, as it contradicts the economic logic of deal-making [10].

Nevertheless, common law does not entirely ignore the pre-contractual stage. It prohibits intentional deception and addresses egregious conduct through legal tools such as pre-contractual documents (e.g., letters of intent, term sheets) and the doctrine of estoppel.

When such documents are present, courts may find that a de facto contractual relationship has arisen and impose corresponding legal obligations.

Of particular importance is the doctrine of *promissory estoppel* [11], developed through case law. It holds that if one party gives another a clear and unequivocal promise, knowing that the other party will rely on it, and the other party does rely on it to their detriment, a court may require the promisor to uphold the promise if justice so demands.

A landmark case is *Hoffman v. Red Owl Stores, Inc.*, where a company promised to grant Hoffman a franchise if he met certain requirements. Relying on this, Hoffman sold his business, relocated, and made substantial investments. Later, the company unreasonably increased the required investment. The court ruled that the initial promises were binding, finding that Hoffman reasonably relied on them [12].

However, courts remain cautious: in the 1990s, only around 8% of *promissory estoppel* claims were successful [13].

It is important to distinguish between pre-contractual liability and a preliminary contract. These are not the same and should not be confused. A preliminary contract is a legally binding agreement in which the parties commit to concluding a main contract in the future on agreed terms (Article 361 of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan). Violation of such an agreement can lead to compelled performance of the promised contract.

By contrast, pre-contractual liability (*culpa in contrahendo*) does not arise from an agreement, but from the fact of entering into negotiations. It is triggered by breaches of duties of good faith and confidentiality at the negotiation stage. Unlike a preliminary contract, there is no agreement to enter into a future contract, only a relationship of trust formed by the parties' conduct.

A preliminary contract is based on expressed mutual intent, and has the required elements of a contract (object, term, form, etc.). The obligation is concrete – to enter into the main contract under certain conditions and within a specified timeframe.

The duties under culpa in contrahendo are general in nature: acting in good faith; providing truthful and complete information; avoiding misleading the counterparty; protecting confidential information; avoiding unjustified termination of negotiations if it would cause harm.

None of these duties requires the conclusion of a contract. On the contrary, the parties retain the freedom to break off negotiations, but they may incur liability for abusing that freedom.

Regarding the conditions for the emergence of pre-contractual liability, there are two key principles, violation of which may cause liability at negotiation stage. They are the principle of good faith during negotiations and the principle of confidentiality of information obtained in the course of such negotiations.

Good faith in negotiations is interpreted broadly both in legal theory and in judicial practice. According to civil law doctrine, three main forms of violating this principle can be distinguished:

1. Entering into negotiations without the intention to conclude a contract.

This refers to situations where one party initiates negotiations without any real desire to reach an agreement, but rather aims, for example, to gain access to commercial information or create an appearance of business activity. For example, company A conducts negotiations with company B regarding equipment supply, while in reality it plans to sign a contract with a different party. The negotiations with B are used solely to exert pressure on pricing.

2. Providing incomplete or false information. This may include the concealment of facts that, by their nature, must be disclosed to enable the other party to make an informed decision. For instance, a seller of real estate fails to inform the buyer that the property is under arrest or encumbered by a mortgage. Such behavior breaches the principle of good faith, as the other party is deprived of the ability to properly assess the transaction risks.

3. Unexpected and unjustified termination of negotiations.

Liability may arise if one party abruptly terminates negotiations without a valid reason at a point where the other party had a reasonable expectation of imminent contract conclusion. For example, the parties have agreed on all essential terms of a lease agreement, and only minor technical refinements remain, but the landlord suddenly refuses to proceed without explanation, despite the tenant having already incurred expenses preparing the premises.

The second ground for the emergence of pre-contractual liability is the *violation of confidentiality obligations*. This is considered a separate and independent basis for pre-contractual liability and arises when one party discloses or unlawfully uses information obtained during the negotiation process. Such conduct typically involves using the information for one's own benefit or disclosing it to third parties without the consent of the other party regardless of whether a contract was ultimately signed.

In practice, there are often situations where a company receives a potential partner's business plan and production technology during negotiations, but then, without concluding a contract, uses that information to launch a similar product under its own brand.

Such conduct is regarded as an independent ground for imposing pre-contractual liability. It is not absorbed by the general principle of good faith, as it pertains to a distinct obligation of confidentiality between the parties.

Foreign Experience

The issue of pre-contractual liability plays a significant role in modern contract theory, as parties often enter into de facto legal relationships during the negotiation stage, creating a risk of harm even in the absence of a finalized agreement. In most developed legal systems, this institution is either codified by law or established through judicial practice. It is most consistently developed in Germany and Italy, and has significantly influenced the formation of similar approaches in Russian legislation.

As previously noted, the German legal system is the birthplace of the doctrine of pre-contractual liability, first articulated in the 19th century by Rudolf von Jhering. He

substantiated the idea that when parties commence negotiations, a special legal obligation arises based on trust and good faith, the breach of which should lead to liability for any resulting damages. This concept was incorporated into § 311(2) of the German Civil Code following the reform of obligations law.

According to § 311(2) of the Code, an obligation involving duties under § 241(2) may arise not only from the conclusion of a contract but also from the initiation of negotiations, preparations for a deal, or similar commercial contacts. The law expressly outlines three grounds for the emergence of such obligations:

1. Initiation of negotiations;
2. Initiation of a contractual relationship whereby one party allows the other to influence its interests;
3. Other similar business contacts [14].

Furthermore, § 311(3) expands the scope of potential participants: pre-contractual obligations may also arise in relation to third parties if they significantly influence the negotiations or benefit from special trust from the counterparty.

Thus, even at the negotiation stage, parties are obliged to act in good faith, take into account each other's legal and financial interests, provide accurate information, and avoid conduct that could harm the other party. Breach of these duties gives rise to liability in the form of compensation for damages, incurred due to reliance on the other party's honesty. As a rule, what is compensated is the negative interest, losses caused by participation in the negotiations, rather than the expected profit from a failed deal.

German case law consistently protects parties harmed by bad faith conduct during negotiations. For example, if one party terminates negotiations without valid reason, knowing that the other has already incurred significant expenses, it must compensate for the resulting damages. The same applies when one party misleads the other about essential aspects of the transaction, conceals risks of contract invalidity, or the loss of a required license. Thus, § 311 of the Code creates a framework where pre-contractual conduct is

evaluated through the lens of the principle of good faith (§ 242), which is a cornerstone of German civil law.

The Italian Civil Code also directly codifies the institution of pre-contractual liability. According to Article 1337 of the *Codice Civile* (“Trattative e responsabilità precontrattuale”), parties are required to act in good faith during negotiations and the formation of a contract [15].

Article 1338 clarifies the consequences of breaching this obligation: a party who knew or should have known of a reason for the future contract’s invalidity and failed to inform the other party must compensate for the resulting damages. Thus, Italian law interprets good faith not only as moral conduct but as an affirmative duty to inform the other party of legal obstacles to the validity of the transaction.

Italian legal doctrine and case law develop this idea further, viewing culpa in contrahendo as a specific form of liability arising from a breach of the general principle of good faith (*buona fede*). Courts recognize that a violation may consist of prolonging negotiations without intent to contract, providing false information, using negotiations to obtain confidential data, or concealing legal or factual issues that prevent the conclusion of the deal.

In terms of compensable damages, Italian law aligns with the German approach, i.e., it compensates losses resulting from unjustified reliance on the partner’s good faith, but not lost profits from a contract that was never concluded. That is, the focus is on the interest in reliance, not the interest in performance.

An important feature of Italian legislation is the connection between Articles 1337 and 1338, while German law bases liability on the general breach of good faith, Italian law specifically outlines liability for failing to disclose contract invalidity, making its regulation more concrete and geared toward protecting trust in the legality of the prospective agreement.

Historically, Russian civil legislation has not contained a direct rule on pre-

contractual liability. However, since the reform of the Civil Code in 2015 (the introduction of Article 434.1 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation), the institution of culpa in contrahendo has actually been implemented into Russian legislation, based on the German-Roman tradition.

According to Article 434.1 of the Code, parties must act in good faith during negotiations and must not engage in conduct that contradicts the established standards of reasonableness and honesty [16]. Paragraph 2 provides examples of bad faith behavior, which includes supplying false information, unjustified termination of negotiations, and concealing facts relevant to the contract's conclusion. The law also establishes an obligation to compensate damages resulting from such violations.

Substantively, the Russian provision mirrors the logic of § 311(2) of German Civil Code and Art. 1337 of Italian Civil Code, but is tailored to the general principles of Russian civil law, where good faith serves as a universal standard for evaluating conduct in civil transactions.

Paragraph 4 of Article 434.1 imposes an obligation on parties not to disclose confidential information received during negotiations regardless of whether a contract is eventually signed. During negotiations, parties often exchange commercially or otherwise valuable information, including technology specifics, pricing strategies, client lists, production processes, and more. Such information is shared in a context of trust, with the understanding that it will be used exclusively for evaluating the feasibility of entering into a contract, not for other purposes.

That is why the law provides a special rule, i.e., if, in the course of negotiations, one party receives information from the other that has been designated as confidential, it must not disclose or misuse it even if the contract is never concluded.

The purpose of this provision is to protect good faith and trust, which form the foundation of civil commerce. Negotiations are not merely an exchange of proposals; they are a process that demands honest and transparent interaction. If parties could not be

confident that the information they provide would remain protected, the negotiation process would become risky and ineffective. Therefore, the duty to maintain confidentiality promotes the stability of business relations and fosters an atmosphere of trust between counterparties.

It is important to note that liability for breach of confidentiality arises regardless of whether a contract is ultimately concluded. This is particularly important because, in real practice, situations often occur where a party uses negotiations as a pretext to obtain commercially valuable information and then terminates discussions, using the acquired data for its own benefit. Such conduct exemplifies bad faith and undermines the principles of equality and fairness between the parties.

A breach of the duty of non-disclosure results in civil liability in the form of compensation for damages. The injured party may claim compensation for losses resulting from the disclosure or improper use of the information, including lost profits and other damages linked to the loss of trade secrets or competitive advantage. It is not necessary to prove the existence of a finalized contract — it is sufficient to establish that the information was transmitted during negotiations, was designated as confidential, and that the other party breached its obligation to protect it.

Foreign experience demonstrates that effective regulation of pre-contractual liability is only possible through a combination of the principle of freedom of contract with the principle of good faith. In all three systems examined (Germany, Italy, Russia), good faith serves as the main criterion. Germany developed a concept that gives legal significance to the initiation of negotiations, while Italy enshrined a similar obligation within the general norms governing contractual negotiations. Russian legislation, having adopted these approaches, created its own model aimed at balancing the freedom to negotiate with the protection of justified reliance.

Conclusion

Thus, the institution of pre-contractual liability constitutes a vital element of modern

civil law, aimed at ensuring a balance between the freedom of contract and the protection of parties' trust during negotiations.

An analysis of the legislation of Uzbekistan shows that, despite the existence of certain provisions regulating bad faith conduct in the conclusion of contracts, there is no comprehensive legal framework governing pre-contractual relations. The current Civil Code of Uzbekistan does not explicitly recognize the doctrine of *culpa in contrahendo*, though its elements are traceable in the provisions on compensation for damages, bad faith, confidentiality, and refusal to conclude a contract.

A comparative legal analysis of the laws of Germany, Italy, and Russia demonstrates that these countries have incorporated the duties of good faith behavior during pre-contractual stages into their systems of obligations law. Common to these systems is the imposition on parties of duties to act honestly, provide accurate information, maintain confidentiality, and compensate damages resulting from the breach of these obligations.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the introduction of a structured legal regime for pre-contractual liability would help to fill existing gaps, reduce the prevalence of bad-faith practices in the market, and enhance legal certainty in civil transactions.

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